

Investigation Status for Collections of Reported UFO Cases: Proposal of a Classification¹

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Abstract

Numerous publications on the UFO subject contain accumulated first-, second- and third-hand reports of UFO sightings. We propose that such reports be subject to a classification system that recognizes how well each case in question has been investigated. The classification is first applied in a German UFO database, which also contains numerous sighting reports from various sources. In this way, pure witness reports can be distinguished from extensively investigated UFO experiences, and the classification can be used to counter the argument that case collections combine heterogeneous statements about UFO sightings according to their origin and thus lose their value.

Motivation

In the evening hours of December 6, 1978, pig farmer Richard Fanning, his wife and two of his friends see a circular white object about three meters wide with two red and two green lights on the top flickering above his barn. The four people drive on in the car while the object appears to follow them for about 50 meters. Then it suddenly turns around and returns to the pigsty, where after a few minutes its lights go out.

Almost thirty years later, on March 22, 2007, in the late evening, Helena K. hears an aircraft-like noise while cleaning her balcony in Rüsselsheim, Germany, and then sees a dark balloon-like body with numerous lights and a diameter of three to four meters at a short distance, which appears to land near her house. The object remains in the same place for about 20 minutes. Only when Ms. K. goes to get a camera does the object disappear after her return.

The preceding two paragraphs are textual reproductions of two UFO sightings at close range (so-called encounters of the first kind, CE I, cf. Hynek, 1972). Although these are only short texts and some details of the sightings are missing, the essential data (reporter, date, location, short description of the experience) are included. Similar descriptions can be found in numerous case catalogs, whether on the internet or as part of books about UFOs.

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The accumulated presentation of UFO cases in this way creates a problem: the origin of the description is unclear and often insufficiently documented. Therefore, the assertion of the existence of countless unexplained UFO cases with reference to case databases is appropriately criticized (e.g. in Peiniger, 2010).

As far as the cases explained above are concerned, an explanation of their origin is intended to show that they were presented as examples to illustrate the problem: The first case was taken from a popular non-fiction book from the USA (Berlitz, 1989, p. 82), in which numerous “inexplicable occurrences” are lined up entirely without reference to any source. The case could not be found in any other source and is possibly a reproduction of a newspaper article or similar.

The case from Rüsselsheim, on the other hand, was cited from the *Journal für UFO-Forschung* and examined by GEP case investigators by telephone, in person and on site at the sighting location (Behne, 2007). This should make it clear that although both UFO cases are similar in the form of their presentation, they are of completely different quality as far as the origin of the content of the statements is concerned (taken from an older book and no longer verifiable after the death of the author vs. verifiably determined by a UFO investigator group in contact with witnesses). The problematic use of case collections with heterogeneous source material, which precisely exhibit the problems of verifying their individual cases explained in the example above, must be improved in future by labeling the origin of the data.

State of the Art

To identify the origin of case data in UFO case collections, an additional classification is required, which is to be assigned after the case investigation or after the case publication. Various proposals already point in this direction.

One such proposal is the “*Investigation Level*” by Bernard Delair and Jenny Randles (Randles and Warrington, 1979, p. 167 f.; Randles and Moore, 2009, p. 21 f.). They distinguish four different levels of investigation in a UFO case, in descending order:

- *Investigation level A*: on-site investigation, personal contact with witnesses, trace evidence if necessary
- *Investigation level B*: telephone or personal contact with witnesses without further investigation
- *Investigation level C*: availability of a completed standard form (questionnaire, structured internet form, etc.)
- *Investigation level D*: existence of exclusively written communication (letters, e-mail, unstructured web forms)
- *Investigation level E*: anecdotal written material from secondary sources (newspapers, magazines, books), no case investigation

A further proposal for classifying the origin of reports is the “*SVP Assessment of Credibility*” according to Jacques Vallée (e.g. Vallée, 1994, p. 254 f.). It gets its name from the three factors *reliability of the source* (S), *on-site visit* (V) and *possible explanations* (P). All three factors can receive a score from zero to four (from 000—unknown / unreliable source, no investigation on site known, natural causes possible, to 444—personal witness interview by reliable source, investigation on site by experienced person, no natural explanation possible).

The factors determined via source, investigation and genuine strangeness are not brought together. Individual assessments that are subjective because they are not described in detail are problematic (in the case of S, for example: What exactly is a source whose reliability is “established”?)

Other suggestions for classifying case material focus more on the assessment of credibility or believability. The number of witnesses, training of the witnesses, apparent strangeness of the cases etc. play a role here, which would go too far for a pure overview of the origin of the case report.

The most elaborate instrument for the assessment of quantitative data on a UFO case is the “*Quantification Method*” developed by Vicente-Juan Ballester Olmos and Miguel Guasp (Ballester Olmos and Guasp, 1988), which collects and weights the three factors quality of information, reliability index and strangeness index via detailed sub-questions and combines them into an overall score. The US UFO research group MUFON has further developed this method and used it for the documentation of its case studies.

MUFON Case Management System
Ballester-Guasp Report Evaluator

<p>Information Quality Index</p> <p>Select the Information gathering method(s) used. (Check all that apply. You must select at least one.)</p> <p>Direct Investigation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> At the site >= 2 hrs <input type="checkbox"/> At the site < 2 hrs <input type="checkbox"/> Person-to-person Interview >= 1 hr <input type="checkbox"/> Person-to-person Interview < 1 hr <input type="checkbox"/> Telephone interview >= 1/2 hr <input type="checkbox"/> Telephone interview < 1/2 hr <p>Indirect Investigation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Questionnaire w/ follow-up Extensive <input type="checkbox"/> Questionnaire w/ follow-up Brief <input type="checkbox"/> Email/Letter/Narrative w/ follow-up Extensive <input type="checkbox"/> Email/Letter/Narrative w/ follow-up Brief <p>Other Investigation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Questionnaire, no follow-up <input type="checkbox"/> Email/Letter/Narrative, no follow-up >= 1 page <input type="checkbox"/> Email/Letter/Narrative, no follow-up < 1 page <input type="checkbox"/> Newspaper >= 500 words <input type="checkbox"/> Newspaper < 500 words <input type="checkbox"/> Radio / TV <input type="checkbox"/> Witness Relative <input type="checkbox"/> Verbal / Rumor / Unknown 	<p>Reliability Index</p> <p>Select Witness Characteristics (You must select one in each section)</p> <p>Number of Witnesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 3 - 5 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 6 - 10 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> More than 10 <p>Witness Profession / Occupation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Not Specified <input type="radio"/> Students <input type="radio"/> Laborers/Farmers/Housewives <input type="radio"/> University Students <input type="radio"/> Traders/Businessmen/Artists <input type="radio"/> Technicians/Police/Pilots <input type="radio"/> Graduates / Military <p>Familial / Social relationship between witnesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Unknown <input type="radio"/> Professional / Co-workers <input type="radio"/> Friends <input type="radio"/> No Relationship <input type="radio"/> Family or Single Witness <p>Geographical relationship at time of sighting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Unknown <input type="radio"/> Together / Single Witness <input type="radio"/> Independent / Separate <p>Witness activity at time of sighting (Main witness)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Not Specified <input type="radio"/> Cultural or Intellectual <input type="radio"/> Recreational <input type="radio"/> At Work (going to or from) <input type="radio"/> Traveling <p>Age of witness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Unknown <input type="radio"/> 35 - 64 <input type="radio"/> Under 10 <input type="radio"/> 65 - 74 <input type="radio"/> 10 - 17 <input type="radio"/> Over 75 <input type="radio"/> 18 - 34 	<p>Strangeness Index</p> <p>What events and/or effects best describe the sighting? (Check all that apply. You must select at least one.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Anomalous appearance <input type="checkbox"/> Existence of anomalous movements <input type="checkbox"/> Apparition of physical-spatial incongruities <input type="checkbox"/> Technological detection <input type="checkbox"/> Close encounter (500 feet or less) <input type="checkbox"/> Presence of beings associated with the UFO <input type="checkbox"/> Finding of traces or production of effects <hr/> <p style="text-align: center;">Optional Information</p> <p>Investigator: <input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/></p> <p>ID #: <input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/></p> <p>Case Number: <input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/></p> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: small;">Open CMS Case File</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="button" value="Submit"/> <input type="button" value="Reset"/> </p> <hr/> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: x-small;"> <input type="button" value="Instructions"/> <input type="button" value="CMS"/> <input type="button" value="MUFON"/> </p>
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Figure 1: Ballester Gualp Report Evaluator on the website of the MUFON Case Management System (MUFON, 2022).

However, simple identification of the cases and an overview of the sub-factors are no longer guaranteed here.

Isaac Koi provides a detailed description of quantitative assessment methods for UFO cases in his comprehensive compilation on UFO case investigation “Best UFO Cases” (Koi, 2011, Parts 19–29).

Classification of the Investigation Status

The classification proposed here to describe the *investigation status* and thus the origin of the data in UFO case collections is based on Delair and Randles' Investigation Level.

However, a classification with letter order from *A* to *D* is difficult for the uninitiated to understand intuitively without consulting the explanation. Regarding the status of the investigation, we distinguish between three main types of report: the anecdotal account, the witness description and the case determined by competent persons. The latter type of case report can then be further refined into three different levels of case investigation, resulting in the following elements of classification:

WR (Written Reproduction)

Entry of an anecdotal account of a UFO sighting from a book, newspaper, or other source without a known investigation of the case.

WA (Witness Account)

Entry of a witness account of a UFO sighting without a known investigation of the case.

IC (Investigated Case)

Entry of the documentation and the result of the case investigation of a UFO sighting by a UFO group or a case investigator.

IC-Q (Quantitative / Questionnaire Investigation)

Entry of the documentation and the result of the case investigation of a UFO sighting by a UFO group or a case investigator by means of a structured questionnaire.

IC-R (Qualitative / Remote Investigation)

Entry of the documentation and the results of the case investigation of a UFO sighting by a UFO group or a case investigator with remote contact to the sighting witness (telephone, e-mail, letter, etc.).

IC-S (On site / Personal Investigation)

Entry of the documentation and the result of the case investigation of a UFO sighting by a UFO group or a case investigator with personal contact to the sighting witness and, if necessary, on-site inspection of the sighting location and securing of evidence.

The refinements of the *IC* classification for identified cases do not include each other, so that, for example, a case initially investigated via questionnaire and then on site can be given the *IC-QS* label. The possible combinations of individual identifiers for investigated cases are then *IC-QR*, *IC-QS*, *IC-RS* and *IC-QRS*.

In contrast to the British investigative level, there is no classification of a one-off contact with a witness without further investigation, such as a one-off call from a witness to a reporting office and immediate conclusion of the investigation. Such cases can be subsumed under the *IC* designation for case investigations that are not described in more detail. As soon as the one-off contact is followed by a responding email from the case investigator, for example, the abbreviation *IC-R* is assigned.

Integration into the UFO Database

The German UFO database considered here was a central archive for UFO sightings in electronic form and had been developed between 2005 and 2007 in cooperation with the

GEP (Czech, 2007). In this UFO database, areas were reserved for the reported cases of German-speaking UFO investigators and groups (the GEP cases can be found in one such area), for European and UFO cases worldwide and for cases of other fringe phenomena. In addition, visitors to the UFO database could register their own UFO sighting and thus make it accessible for contact and processing by a UFO group or a case investigator.

Since December 2010, the classification of investigation status shown here has been implemented as a database field in the UFO database for all UFO case collections (UFO database, 2010). New cases entered into the database can be classified immediately (own sightings entered by website visitors automatically receive the classification WR). Existing cases from UFO groups, case investigators or German, European and worldwide cases taken from other sources are gradually assigned the classification.

In this way, the investigation status finds practical application in the UFO database. In the future, it will be possible to assess the quality of the numerous cases of different origins that are now available in this database immediately. It will then even be possible to carry out evaluations such as determining the percentage of all WR, all WA or all IC cases and their subtypes in comparison with each other or with the rest of the database. Arguments relating to collections of cases can then be made based on precisely the category that is relevant to them, as opposed to a generalized view of all cases. For example, it can be shown that many case collections only contain WR case types, or statements about unexplained UFO cases can be based on the subset of all data records that contain the IC-S label and therefore represent cases with sufficient validity.

UFO - Sichtung

A: Allgemeine Sichtungsdaten

Fall Nummer:	20100115
Fall Nummer neu:	
Sichtungsdatum:	15.01.2010
Sichtungszeit:	00.00 - 05.30 MEZ
Postleitzahl:	76297
Sichtungsort	Stutensee-Friedrichstal
Geokoordinaten:	Länge: Breite:
Bundesland:	Baden Württemberg
Sichtungsland:	Deutschland
Zeugen:	3
Klassifikation: (Erklärung)	NL
Bewertung: (Erklärung)	
Identifikation:	
Ermittlungen:	
Untersuchungsstatus: (Erklärung)	Witness Account – WA
Untersucher:	
Quelle:	Meldung an UFO-Datenbank.de
Druckerfreundliche Ansicht:	Zum Bericht Bericht ohne Bilder

B: Sachverhalt

Mehrere Objekte die den Anschein machen Sterne zu sein, dafür aber zu groß sind und stark in verschiedenen Farben blinken und wechseln (rot, orang, gelb, grün und weiß).
 Anfang hielten meine Freundin und mein Kumpel es für Sterne, bei genauerer Beobachtung stellte man aber fest, dass diese Objekte sich nicht wie Sterne verhielten. Sie wandern nicht oder wenn dann unregelmäßig. Manchmal sind sie bei klaren Wetter zuerkenne, manchmal aber nicht. Das Auftreten hat also nichts mit sternenklarem Himmel oder bezogenem Himmel zu tun oder Jahreszeiten sondern ist einfach unregelmäßig. Interessant ist auch das sie manchmal, obwohl es klarer Himmel ist, einfach "verschwinden" und dann urplötzlich wieder auftauchen, als wenn sie ihr Licht einfach "an- und ausschalten" würden.

Dauer ist unterschiedlich, teilweise zwischen 4-5.5 Stunden
 Himmelsrichtung, ist unterschiedlich, hauptsächlich aber Norden, da in diese Richtung mein Fenster ausgerichtet ist.
 Zeugen drei.

Figure 2: Example of a UFO report classified as WA in the German UFO database.

Connection to the GEP's Witness Contact Documentation

Documentation on GEP case investigations is provided with the so-called first contact description in the *Journal für UFO-Forschung* and in the UFO database (Peiniger, 2006). Through the application this—a chronological list of contacts with the witness using abbreviations for all possible forms of contact or case investigation—makes it clear how the reporter contacted the GEP and how the UFO report was subsequently processed.

The abbreviations used for this description are *br* (contact by letter), *em* (contact by e-mail), *Falldatenb.* (report via the UFO database), *tel* (telephone contact), *p* (personal contact), *fb* (completed questionnaire), *vo* (on-site visit) and *sps* (forensics). The designation *p* or *sps* automatically includes *vo*.

An example of an initial contact description is 18.3.2009 – *tel / p / sps / tel / em*. The initial contact was thus made by the witness calling the GEP on March 18, 2009, further processing took place in person, by telephone and finally by e-mail. In addition, a forensic investigation was carried out on site after the personal contact. (According to Behne, 2007, the first contact description of the UFO report from Rüsselsheim described at the beginning is then incidentally April 27, 2007 – *tel / tel / p*).

It can be seen from the description of the initial contact description that this is also aimed at explaining the status of the investigation of a UFO case. This results in overlaps with the investigation status classification presented here. A first contact description 29.3.2010 – *em / tel / p / em* can also be described by *IC-RS*; both classifications make it clear here that a case investigation was carried out via remote and personal contact. However, the initial contact contains more precise and time-specific information; in contrast to the initial contact, the *IC-RS* information does not specify when exactly the witness made contact, the sequence of further contacts and the form of remote contact. Therefore, the classification of the examination status cannot replace the initial contact description. However, both details can be used as required for the publication of case documentation in various media. For example, the initial contact can still be noted for the detailed case description in the *Journal für UFO-Forschung*, while the classification of the examination status is used in cumulative case sketches such as in special publications or the UFO database, where non-GEP cases are also recorded for which no detailed initial contact description is available.

Summary and Outlook

This article has presented a classification method for the origin and investigation effort for descriptions of UFO cases, the *investigation status*. It is used in the UFO database and thus also in GEP case descriptions.

At the same time, there are other classifications for the origin of case data, some of which also make it possible to quantify credibility or believability. Due to the status of the UFO topic as lay research and the associated hurdles, it is not to be expected that the many case classifications used worldwide for limited numbers of case collections, whether for before or after case investigation, will ever be replaced by standardized forms.

However, the variants presented for describing the origin of the data, including the proposed investigation status, can be combined within certain limits. The aim of an effective classification of the data origin in case collections, a quick overview of the source and validity of the statements made about a reported UFO sighting and thus a differentiated assessment of case collections, can be achieved using the described labels.

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